

On a Qubit Specific Functionality of the 2DEG Differential Mobility Sign

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Principle of Operation

Having investigated [<https://doi.org/10.4236/opj.2011.14033> and References 7., 8., 14., 16., 18., 19. therein] the Nanoheterointerfacial Two-Dimensional Electron Gas (2DEG) Dynamics systematically in the past, we are currently examining the prospect of an additional applicability of its; how monitoring the respective Differential Mobility Sign (DMS) at Constant appropriate Ambient Temperature and within the framework of Cypher-dictated successive Cumulative Photon Doses would enable the characterisation of a pertinent Optical Telecommunication environment through allowing for the tracking of whether the Fundamental or the First Excited 2DEG Functional Eigenstate (FE) would be the Actually Significant (AS) one: Thus, it is envisaged that the 2DEG DMS will be exhibiting a Qubit specific functionality denoting the Link's Output in terms of the 2DEG AS FE consequent upon the Effective Photonic Signals. Furthermore, it is hoped that a Modular Set-Up deriving from the above Entity will be offering innovative Quantum Information Registering.